

Compilation of the 21 Commandments Mentioned in the Discussion of the Exemption of Women from Time-Bound Mitzvot in b. Qiddushin 33b–35a and b. Berakhot 20b With Torah Verses and Groups of Addressees
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Legend left column

Non-time-bound commandment: woman obligated (7)

Time-bound commandment: woman not obligated (7)

Time-bound commandment: woman obligated (4)

Non-time-bound commandment: woman not obligated (3)

Numeration Sefer Hahinukh*

Numeration Sefer Hamitzvot*

🕒 Time-bound

⊕ Non-time-bound

Legend second column from left

[] = Verses preceding or following the relevant verse will appear in square brackets with a smaller font.

Legend third column from left

The groups of addressees most frequently listed in the context of mitzvot are highlighted in color:

Israel (ישראל)

People of Israel (בני ישראל)

People (עם)

Other (groups of) addressees

[] = Verses preceding or following the relevant verse will appear in square brackets with a smaller font.

Biblical quotes are based on *The New Oxford Annotated Bible: New Revised Standard Version, With The Apocrypha*, eds. Michael D. Coogan et al. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010; *emphasis vr.*

* The first known systematic listings of the entirety of the Torah’s commandments – 613 according to amoraic Rabbi Simlai (B. Makkot 23b) – and the verses behind them date to the Middle Ages. Due to their familiarity, two of these sources – although anachronistic – are referred to in this compilation: Sefer Hamitzvot and Sefer Hahinukh. The Sefer Hamitzvot is composed of two sections: “Prescriptions” (P 1–248) and “Proscriptions” (N 1–365). The Sefer Hahinukh is structured chronologically according to the Torah verses on which the precepts are based and is numbered consecutively from 1 through 613. Quotes from Sefer Hamitzvot are based on the database *Responsa*; English translation: Maimonides, *Sefer Hamitzvoth*, Translated by Shraga Silverstein, 2 vols. New York: Moznaim, 1993; quotes from the Sefer Hahinukh are based on *Sefer haHinnuch: The Book of [Mitzvah] Education*, Ascribed to Rabbi Aaron haLévi of Barcelona, With a Translation and Notes by Charles Wengrov, 5 vols. Jerusalem: Feldheim, 1978–1989.

Commandment	Torah verse on which the commandment is based (according to Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot)	Groups of addressees/ verse	Discussed in tractates Qiddushin and Berakhot
Procreation ⊕ 1 P 212	Gen 1:28: God blessed them [male and female (זכר ונקבה); Gen 1:27]: and God said to them: “Be fruitful and multiply and fill the earth and subdue it (...).”	Humankind (אדם) (...): male and female; Gen 1:27: So God created humankind in his image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34a–35a In addition i.a.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Yevamot 6:6 • b. Yevamot 65b
Matzah (at the seder) ⊕ 10 P 158	Exod 12:18: In the first month, from the evening of the fourteenth day until the evening of the twenty-first day, you shall eat unleavened bread.	The whole congregation of Israel; Exod 12:3: (...) Tell [Moses and Aaron; Exod 12:1] the whole congregation of Israel (...). (speech Exod 12:2–12:20)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34a–35a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) In addition i.a.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Pesahim 2:22 • b. Pesahim 91b • y. Pesahim 8:1 (35d)
To sanctify the day ⊕ 31 P 155	Exod 20:8: Remember the sabbath day, and keep it holy.	People; Exod 19:25: So Moses went down to the people and told them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Berakhot 20b In addition i.a.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Shevu'ot 20b
Fearing father and mother ⊕ 212 P 211	Lev 19:3: You shall each (אישי) revere your mother and father, and you shall keep my sabbaths: I am the Lord your God.	All the congregation of the people of Israel; Lev 19:2: Speak to all the congregation of the children of Israel and say to them: (...). (speech ends in Lev 19:37)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:11 • b. Qiddushin 31b; 34b–35a In addition i.a.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sifra: parasha Kedoshim
Lulav ⊕ 324 P 169	Lev 23:40: On the first day you shall take the fruit of majestic trees, branches of palm trees, boughs of leafy trees, and willows of the brook; and you shall rejoice before the Lord your God for seven days.	People of Israel; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the children of Israel (...). (speech ends in Lev 23:43)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 33b • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) In addition i.a.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Sukkah 3:12; 3:15 • b. Sukkah 42a; 44a

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<p><i>Sukkah</i> 🕒 325 P 168</p>	<p>Lev 23:42: You shall live in booths for seven days; all that are citizens in Israel shall live in booths, [23:43] so that your generations may know that I made the children of Israel live in booths when I brought them out of the land of Egypt: I am the Lord your God.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Lev 23:34: Speak [Moses; Lev 23:33] to the children of Israel (...). (speech ends in Lev 23:43) All that are citizens (כל-האזרח); Lev 23:42: (...) all that are citizens in Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 33b–34a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Sukkah 28a–b
<p><i>Tzitzit</i> 🕒 386 P 14</p>	<p>Num 15:38: Speak to the people of Israel and tell them to make fringes on the corners of their garments throughout their generations and to put a blue cord on the fringe at each corner.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Num 15:38: Speak to the people of Israel (...). (speech ends in Num 15:41)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • b. Qiddushin 33b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sifre Numeri on Num 15:38 • b. Menahot 43a
<p>Redemption of the firstborn ⊕ 392 P 80</p>	<p>Num 18:15: The first issue of the womb of all creatures, human and animal, which is offered to the Lord, shall be yours; but the firstborn of human beings you shall redeem, and the firstborn of unclean animals you shall redeem.</p>	<p>Aaron; Num 18:8: The Lord spoke to Aaron: (...). (speech ends in Num 18:19)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 29a; 34a–35a <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Bekhorot 47b
<p><i>Shofar</i> 🕒 405 P 170</p>	<p>Num 29:1: On the first day of the seventh month you shall have a holy convocation; you shall not work at your occupations. It is a day for you to blow the trumpets.</p>	<p>People of Israel; Num 28:2: Command [Moses; Num 28:1] the people of Israel, and say to them: (...). (speech ends in Num 29:39)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 33b • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Rosh Hashanah 2:5 • b. Rosh Hashanah 33a • b. Eruvin 96b

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<p>Talmud torah ⌚ 419 P 11</p>	<p>Deut 6:7: Recite them to your children (לבינך) and talk about them [these words; Deut 6:6] when you are at home and when you are away, when you lie down and when you rise.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 31:12: (...) so that they may hear and learn (...); (people in Deut 31:12).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך [ובן-בנך])]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:11 • b. Qiddushin 29a–b; 34a–35a; 40b • b. Berakhot 20b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Horayot 3:8 • m. Sotah 3:4 • Sifre on Deut 6:7 • y. Sotah 3:4/7 (19a)
<p>Shema ⌚ 420 P 10</p>	<p>Deut 6:7: Recite them to your children (לבינך) and talk about them [these words; Deut 6:6] when you are at home and when you are away, when you lie down and when you rise.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך [ובן-בנך])]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Berakhot 1:1–2; 3:3 • t. Berakhot 3:1 • b. Berakhot 20b–21a • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b)
<p>Tefillin ⌚ Tefillin for the hand: 421 P 13 Tefillin for the head: 422 P 12</p>	<p>Deut 6:8: Bind them [these words; Deut 6:6] as a sign on your hand, fix them as an emblem on your forehead (...).</p> <p>Maimonides points out to three repetitions of the commandment in Exod 13:9 and 13:16 (people in Exod 13:3) and in Deut 11:18 (Israel in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך [ובן-בנך])]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 34a–35a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • m. Berakhot 3:3 • b. Berakhot 20b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Eruvin 96a–b • Mekhilta de-Rabbi Yishmael: tractate Pis'cha: chapter 17 on Exod 13:9

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<p><i>Mezuzah</i> ⊕ 423 P 15</p>	<p>Deut 6:9: (...) and write them [these words; Deut 6:6] on the doorposts of your house and on your gates.</p> <p>Maimonides points out to a repetition of the commandment in Deut 11:20: Write them on the doorposts of your house and on your gates (<i>Israel</i> in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p><i>Israel</i>; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך [ויבן-בנך])]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34a–b • m. Berakhot 3:3 • b. Berakhot 20b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b) <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mekhilta de-Rabbi Yishmael: tractate Pis'cha: chapter 17 on Exod 13:9 • b. Pesachim 4a
<p><i>Birkat hamazon</i> ⊕ 430 P 19</p>	<p>Deut 8:10: You shall eat your fill and bless the Lord your God for the good land that he has given you.</p>	<p><i>Israel</i>; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...). [6:2: you and your children and your children's children (אתה ובנך [ויבן-בנך])]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Berakhot 3:3 • b. Berakhot 20b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b)
<p><i>To serve God</i> ⊕ * 433 P 5</p> <p>* The time-boundness of this commandment has been subject of controversy among the rabbis (see Ellinson 1986, 171f.)</p>	<p>Deut 10:20: You shall fear the Lord your God; him alone you shall worship; to him you shall hold fast, and by his name you shall swear. (<i>Sefer Hahinukh</i>)</p> <p>Exod 23:25: You shall worship the Lord your God, and I will bless your bread and your water; and I will take sickness away from among you. (<i>Sefer Hamitzvot</i>)</p> <p>Repetitions of the commandment are pointed out in both Sefer Hahinukh and Sefer Hamitzvot, for example in Deut 6:13 and 11:13 (<i>Israel</i> in Deut 5:1).</p>	<p><i>Israel</i>; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p> <p><i>People of Israel</i>; Exod 20:19/22:* The Lord said to Moses: Thus you shall say to the people of Israel: (...). (speech ends in Exod 23:33) [Exod 22:30/31*: You shall be people consecrated (אנשי-קדש) to me.]</p> <p>* (different numeration depending on bible edition)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Berakhot 3:3 • b. Berakhot 20b • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b)

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<p>To rejoice on the festivals</p> <p>⌚</p> <p>488</p> <p>P 54</p>	<p>Deut 16:14: Rejoice during your festival, you and your sons and your daughters, your male and female slaves, as well as the Levites, the strangers, the orphans, and the widows resident in your towns.</p> <p><i>[Deut 16:1f.: Pessach; 16:10f.: Shavuot; 16:13: Sukkot]</i></p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34a–35a <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Hagigah 6b • b. Pesahim 109a
<p>Re'iyah (to appear in the Tempel three times a year)</p> <p>⌚</p> <p>489</p> <p>P 53</p>	<p>Deut 16:16: Three times a year all your males (כל-זכורך) shall appear before the Lord your God at the place that he will choose: at the festival of unleavened bread, at the festival of weeks, and at the festival of booths.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34b <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Hagigah 1:1 • Mekhilta de-Rabbi Yishmael: tractate Pis'cha: chapter 17 on Exod 13:9 • b. Eruvin 96a–b • b. Hagigah 4a; 6b
<p>To return a lost object</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>538</p> <p>P 204</p>	<p>Deut 22:1: You shall not watch your neighbor's ox or sleep straying away and ignore them; you shall take them back to their owner.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 34a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 61c 11–17 • y. Berakhot 3:3 6b
<p>To release the mother bird</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>545</p> <p>P 148</p>	<p>Deut 22:6–7: If you come on a bird's nest, in any tree or on the ground, with fledglings or eggs, with the mother sitting on the fledglings or on the eggs, you shall not take the mother with the young. Let the mother go, taking only the young for yourself, in order that it may go well with you and you may live long.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 34a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • y. Berakhot 3:3 6b

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<p>Make a guard rail around flat roofs</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>546</p> <p>P 184</p>	<p>Deut 22:8: When you build a new house, you shall make a parapet for your roof; otherwise you might have bloodguilt on your house, if anyone should fall from it.</p>	<p>Israel; Deut 5:1: Moses convened all Israel, and said to them: Hear, O Israel (...). (speech ends in Deut 26:19); Deut 6:4: Hear, O Israel: (...); Deut 10:12: So now, O Israel (...).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t. Qiddushin 1:10 • b. Qiddushin 34a • y. Qiddushin 1:7 (61c) • y. Berakhot 3:3 (6b)
<p>Hakhei</p> <p>⊕</p> <p>612</p> <p>P 16</p>	<p>Deut 31:12: Assemble (הקהל) the people – men, women, and children, as well as the aliens residing in your towns – so that they may hear and learn to fear the Lord your God and to observe diligently all the words of his law.</p>	<p>Priest, elders; Deut 31:9–10: Then Moses wrote down this law, and gave it to the priests, the sons of Levi, who carried the ark of the covenant of the Lord, and to all the elders of Israel. Moses commanded them (...). People (<i>men, women, children, aliens</i>); Deut 31:12: Assemble the people – men, women, and children, as well as the aliens (...). (speech ends in Deut 31:13)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b. Qiddushin 34a–35a <p>In addition i.a.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m. Sotah 7:8 • b. Sotah 41a–42a